

From a One-Off European Windfall Levy on Energy Excess Profits towards a European Sovereign Fund

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Summary

1. This policy paper elaborates on the architecture of a European Sovereignty Fund (ESF), shedding light on the critical issue of funding such an initiative.
2. It proposes an one-off levy on the excess profit in the energy sector, building on the concept of the Ricardian economic rent.
3. The ESF can be instrumental in identifying and financing strategic projects, including those in the Important Projects of Common European Interest (IPCEI's) list, that would make EU member-stated less dependable to supply-chains disruptions.

1. Introduction

The US Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) has stirred economic discomfort in the EU, where it is perceived as an explicit industrial endeavor under the guise of fiscal policy. The US legislation now recognizes the urgency for a federal climate change policy away from fossil fuels towards renewable energy. A muscled budget of 369 billion dollar will substantially subsidize its business sector to facilitate the transition. Take as an example the promotion of electric vehicles where the IRA offers ample tax credits for consumers to support 'made in the USA'. This additional stimulus comes on top of its comparative advantage as the US is already better endowed with natural resources.

Legitimately the EU worries that these initiatives – laudable as they are in their own right – will jeopardize the level playing field with the US in terms of economic competitiveness. What can Europe do? As a first concern a green subsidy race, detrimental to the economies both in the US and the EU, should be contained. And as a collateral damage a fierce fragmentation between the political leaders of the member states itself should be avoided.

At the level of more prospective actions this policy paper elaborates on the architecture of a European Sovereignty Fund (ESF), as signaled by the European Commission in the 'State of the Union' (September 14, 2022). The critical issue is the initial funding of the ESF. Here it will be argued that a slice of a one-off levy on the

excess profit in the energy sector could fill the gap.

2. Why a European one-off levy?

Windfall gains happen in economic history: extraordinary surges in profits of companies and industries. These excess profits cannot be assigned to an astute management, superior investment or innovative development with a touch of genius. They just emerge from external events beyond the realm of adequate regular firm governance. A case in point are the spikes in gas prices, due to economic demand, since the beginning of 2022. Certainly the record gains are reinforced by the violent invasion of Russia in Ukraine.

These enormous profits do not get unnoticed and are in shrill contrast with the fall in real purchasing power of the ordinary people that may lead to energy poverty. In several countries of the EU one has noticed a growing pression on policy makers to act and tax the windfall profits of the companies in gas, oil and electricity production. The argument usually runs in terms of fairness and is supported by the public at large. On the other side, windfall taxes are contested by the industry as they fuel ambiguity and uncertainty for a given tax legislation when such a levy is imposed ex post.

This policy brief articulates an economic reasoning based on the related but broader concept of economic rent. Ricardian land rents are the canonical example in the standard economic literature. At the level of intuition one can consider two farmers with equal skills and efforts. Both cultivate a piece of land with the same surface (*ceteris paribus* hypothesis). The only dominant difference is the fertility of the soil. Assume further that the farmer with a mediocre quality of the soil grows enough grain to feed his own family.

The farmer with the better piece benefits from an additional production which he can sell on the market. This is the essence of differences in economic land rents which accrue to a farmer.

An actual and concise definition of economic rents can be formulated as: “they are any payments that accrue to someone for doing something that exceed what would have induced them to do so” (P. Collier, 2018). Switching from ethics to economics, the concept of economic rents becomes instrumental for a one-off levy on excess profits. Unlike many other forms of taxation a windfall tax on rents does not entail collateral damages in efficiency losses. By definition a levy on rents, in principle, does not affect the decisions on efforts in economic activities. Elaborating further on the insight of Ricardo, the so-called Henry George theorem proved – in a more formal and generalised way – that taxing economic rents is a superior target on the criterion of efficiency (R. Arnott and J. Stiglitz, 1979).

In this policy brief a one-off tax is assessed in economic terms next to ethical arguments. In our view such a tax is better levied at the EU-level – rather than by the individual member states – in order to safeguard the level playing field. What about the proceeds of such a levy? Own revenues for the EU budget are a possible candidate. One recalls the historic decision by the European Council to launch a 750 billion euro recovery plan (July 21, 2020), now labelled as the Recovery and Resilience Facility. With links to the Multiannual Financial Framework (2022-2027) also more elbow room for new own resources was conceded for the European budget.

One can envisage a staggered formula for the allocation of proceeds, as we will argue later on. One part for the EU as such and a second layer as a temporary targeted grant to the member states to alleviate somehow the

energy concerns in their own country. The first slice can then be channeled to the ESF for initial funding.

3. Towards a European Sovereign Fund

From the perspective of future reactions against the IRA the proposal for a new European Sovereignty Fund (ESF) can play a pivotal role. At the outset, almost unnoticed in the media, the Presidential Address explicitly mentioned that the President of the Commission will push to create a new ESF (page 17 of the State of the Union 2022). In this section I'll elaborate somewhat on the concept reporting closely on the original phrasing of the Presidential Address.

How can the Commission design and construct such a new EU-vehicle? Let us start from an empirical observation and a clearer definition of the ultimate goal. At the geopolitical level one is confronted with a shortage of rare materials. As it stands now 80 pct. of the batteries are produced by Chinese firms. Worldwide the same concentration, roughly the same percentage, holds for the processing of lithium, cobalt and nickel. It is expected that the Green Deal will move ahead so much that by 2030 the EU demand for those critical materials will increase fivefold.

Europe learned from the present fossil fuel crisis that too much dependence on too little credible suppliers can entail invasive economic risks. So Europe has to avoid falling in the same dependency as with gas and oil. Its links with reliable countries and key growth regions need to be updated. In the same vein the President announced a European critical Raw Materials Act.

The ESF can be instrumental in identifying strategic projects all along the supply chain, from extraction to refining, from processing to recycling. And also to build

up strategic reserves where adequate supply is at risk. To achieve this ambition financial participations in Important Projects of Common European Interest (IPCEI's) are envisaged. As an example it is reported that hydrogen can be a game changer for Europe. In this domain an IPCEI has already been decided to move the hydrogen economy from niche to scale. This project benefits from 5.2 billion euro from the member states and 7.2 billion euro from the partners of the private sector. Similar IPCEI's can in the future be located under the ESF umbrella.

4. A financial link between the two endeavors

Practical matters still need to be clarified. The notion of the actual excess profits as an economic rent may help to calculate the taxable base of a company. As a numerical example one can calculate the average realized profit of the last five years. Eventually this figure may be upgraded for inflation and some other relevant factors. The difference between the figure of a 'normal' profit and the latest estimate of the record profit for 2022 can be interpreted as a proxy for the economic rent, i.e. the taxable base.

As a next step the percentage of the levy itself has to be decided. Some rumors circle around 33 pct. Other economists favor a higher percentage up to 90 pct. The argument being that the levy on an economic rent does not in principle hurt economic incentives. Like always in practical policy making, all these parameters have to be decided in a tedious political 'tâtonnement process' supported by qualified expertise.

In our proposal it stands out that a significant tranche of the proceeds should be channeled into the original funding to the ESF. If policy makers in the EU convincingly seek to develop the ESF into a substantial

strategic wealth fund, then this financial muscle is required from the beginning.

Earlier attempts to promote some type of a European Wealth Fund suffered from a lack of enthusiasm from the member states (e.g. P. Vanhoudt and W. Moesen 2021). One can understand that, in the context of galloping deficits and debt levels, the national governments were reluctant to issue additional bonds for the initial funding of a vague vehicle. This time is different: the objective of the ESF is adequately defined and the means can come from a one-off levy on windfall profits in the energy sector.

5. Conclusions

What are the other alternatives for the funding at the outset of the ESF? A reshuffle within the EU budget may be a possible candidate. But the slack means seem to lack opulence. Moreover they are subject to an onerous political reallocation, crowding out other outlays. The same holds for eventual remnant means from the European Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF). Another suggestion originates from the European Stability Mechanism (ESM), established during the sovereign debt crisis (2011-2015) to support Greece and some other vulnerable member states. Apparently the ESM could also engage for some supplementary funding. Of course all means can help. But the more adequate channel boils down to the proceeds from a slice of a one-off levy on the excess profits in the energy sector.

Ending with the political decision making in the EU it is well known that progress ultimately depends on the cohesion between France and Germany. Hopefully the recent meeting in Paris between Macron and Scholz (January 22 of this year) may endorse the Jean Monnet quote: “l’Europe se fera dans les crises et elle sera la sommation des réponses à ses crises”.

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